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'What's due is residue': Historical and Environmental Melancholia within The Broken Vessel exhibition

By Dr Dina Zoe Belluigi

Part I

Figure 1: A view across parts of the installation of the Broken Vessels exhibition (Image by Brent Mestre, Connemara, 2021)

Broken

In the distance fragmented words scratch and bark over truncated logs, covered in mushrooms and slime. At the point where an encroaching forest overtakes the detritus of a rusted tower, emerge the phrases:

ahistorical darkness...

more futuristic than lost tomorrows...

heritage and mirage...

scrape up the rape....

What's due is residue...¹

A thickly accented incantation, unmistakably of a Black South African, cajoles the invisible audience to come closer. To hear this transmission, I must leave the safety of the formalist building and approach a field of circular structures, lined as if pews in a derelict cathedral set within a forest clearing.

I make my way gingerly across the eroded car park, entering where a jet of holy water squirts in my peripheral vision. Along the central aisle, a water furrow reflects a procession of fluttering specters. I pick my way, cautiously around pine saplings, uneven mounds of graded stone, indentations from metal corners and stains of pigment on the once-soft bog soil. To be able to hear requires that I hold my breath. I crouch intimately close to the hand-sized radios to distinguish the human message from bird cries, the whining of distant chain-saws, and the dripping and creaking of the emptied-out tank which looms ominously above.

Welcome to your own perceptions misconceptions.

Final wretchedness in existence...

Blood-paths we

travelled/covered map your guilt's extent...¹

I have heard this voice before – it is specific to a legendary soothsayer, an outcast poet. I remind myself that here, far away from the land of our country, he calls not only to me nor the arriving congregation, but also to his fellow artists performing this rite of declaration and collective self-flagellation. Sharing secrets, regrets and accusations in the hope of absolution or redemption.

Impossibility

Gravity lifts us

They meditate to levitate see how free they fall...

Slavery keeps them grounded

free see how they trip and fall.

Prepared for war? No.

Prepared roar to be served up on God's dinner tables.

No fable this.¹

I turn, seeking out the imagery I recalled passing, glimpsed on the indigo adornments of the central aisle. A sleeping figure levitates over the pyramid beneath her. The once great roars of righteous anger and solidarity now reduced to aural and visual vibrations of dissent, pathos, regret at the brutal realities of the post-apocalyptic landscape. The notable tenor struck by the poet Rampolokeng resonated across the show.

raised the fist to sell...

they deface the freedom dream...

The revolution dream slimmest chances of survival for the suicidal

mute fade stagnant work toward critics dictate

nothing to create redundant¹.

And such began my experience of this art exhibition: moving through a site where the natural world has been eroded and mis-shaped by the activities and monuments of human interest, to engage with artistic interventions about delusions of the authority and creativity of the human. A fragment of one artwork seemingly connected fleetingly with another; some elements repeated across eleven artworks, as if the six heterogeneous artists were in agreement. Some aspects are

disruptively strange, out of place murmurs of disquiet in the obscure Inagh Valley. The arrangement evoked one of the many ruined cathedrals which have grown over time across the island of Ireland, where the overlapping graves of opportunists awaiting the day of judgment are strewn haphazardly, in disrepair. There is integrity in the weariness of this show of 'Broken Vessels', situated at the most western margin of western Europe. Artists laying bare the failed grand dreams of human progress, development and democracy, of science and of the arts, and the costs of denuding the world. Each work contained a sense of reckoning that this is "no fable this"¹.

Figure 2: Details of visual detritus of the history of the site, including architectural schema (left top and bottom), labels of the now-defunct salmon hatchery (bottom right), and prior artists' materials (right) (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

Vessels

The title of the exhibition provides many clues to the questions which underpinned its curatorial impulse. I have split *Broken vessels* to explore openings between and across the two words.

2021 was two years into a global pandemic possibly caused by human interruption of the natural world. It was a period which once again exposed the hollowness of international commitments to human rights and sustainable development, as vaccine imperialism and geopolitics reasserted the disregard of the majority world by dominant minority powers. The common good of global health was trumped by the capitalist interests in intellectual property. It was two decades into a millennium where environmental crises were not only foretold but experienced; and after two thirds of a century into

structural decolonization continually thwarted, with reminders of continued racism and Afropessimism in the West reasserted by movements such as Black Lives Matter the year before. Global capitalism continued to squeeze the natural and human worlds in its destructive grip; with digital technology recognized as both a blessing and a curse.

Into this moment, the South African artist-curator invoked a response by fellow artists to be situated in a remote location on the island of Ireland. The disparities between what was occurring on the southern tip of the continent of Africa and the most western region of Europe, were worlds apart.

Were they being asked to respond to the brokenness of the site? To circular structures, underground bunkers and disused tanks which once housed an inland fish hatchery and research facility? Were the artworks they were to create broken vessels in themselves, designed specifically to leak their content into the receptacles of the viewers' consciousness? Or was this term a naming of the artists themselves, as creative agents born in the aftermath of the demise of historical and environmental hope?

As an island surrounded by oceans and seas, the word 'vessel' would evoke nautical associations of ships and containers for local inhabitants, perhaps of the ghost vessels that throughout history have somehow reached the Irish shoreline empty of people and of explanation². Ship vessels brought migrant invaders and planters; they took away many local migrants to form the Irish diaspora, settling with or without belonging in England, and claiming varied identities and relations further away as settler colonialists across the world, including in Africa. Inevitably, a contemporary exhibition of 'broken vessels' with 'African' artists would evoke the flimsy boats which encapsulate the aspirations of the thousands of migrants barred from safe entry to Europe, whose lives are the cost of the hostile environment of the United Kingdom who regulate Northern Ireland's borders and seas.

Vessels have allusions to definitions within natural science. When describing the anatomical structures of living organisms, including that of animals within zoology and plants within botany, a 'vessel' names the ducts and canals which convey or hold life-giving or sustaining fluid, including water, blood, minerals and nutrients. To be broken would then suggest damage done or a wound inflicted, with the spillage of fluids and even the threat of death. The curator's notes indicate that there was interest in such corporeal associations,

The vessel like the body, the container of the life-force of water and blood are deeply embedded in the recesses of our cultural, religious and mythological narratives that interweave through us passing from mouth to ear, from hand to body. The crafting or manufacturing of the vessel; be it with, mud, wood, skin, steel, plastic or glass; contain, hold, embrace and preserve, carry that which we have harvested, collected or made, from which we take and ingest back into our bodies.³

Vessels are also objects which hold liquid, as holders or containers.

Often round or in-the-round, oval, a calabash, made of skin, of caste-iron, a cauldron. Harboring water, blood, fat, pigment and seed.³

In naming calabashes and cauldrons, the curator knowingly recalls historic artefacts from South African and Irish history. The calabash, one of the first plants cultivated for its properties of holding water, was a central enabler for surviving migration across the harsh desert conditions by the indigenous peoples of South Africa, who faced genocide in the 19th century. In the legends of diasporic Africans displaced to North America, the calabash is a vessel of wisdom and knowledge⁴. Large cauldrons called 'famine pots' are displayed at the very front of small towns in western Ireland, in commemoration of their use in soup kitchens during the *An Gorta Mór* ('The Great Hunger')⁵. Within the popular memory of that period⁶, such international aid interventions were marred by controversy as in some instances such relief and also education was provided on condition of conversion from the Catholic to Protestant denomination, from which emerged the derogatory accusation 'took the soup' and the term 'souperism'⁷ to describe the phenomenon. Neither calabash nor cauldron are in contemporary use - instead the objects serve as vessels of collective memory of the tenuousness of human survival. Connections of solidarity between the two countries have been explicitly marked. In one instance this involved

walking the landscape and monumentalizing loss and resistance, undertaken by the late Archbishop Desmond Tutu with an Irish organization of which he was a patron⁸ when The Dunnes Stores Strikers erected a monument in the year of South Africa's first democratic election.

The round tanks on the site were once vessels too - holders of water as part of the promise of fish production to invigorate a flagging rural economy and as an alternative source in the face of depleting oceanic fish stocks. Now the tanks only occasionally hold rainwater. The curator had seen and engaged with one such tank when he created *Glynsk* (2018), a black and white film which evoked sinking of the Titanic, one of the most grandiose spectacles of human technological folly and failure, when in residency at The Inagh Valley. Having resided for some time in Belfast, a city profiting from 'dark tourism' commemorations which extends to the ship yard where the Titanic was constructed⁹, the artist interiorizes that moment, making it small, intimate, painful again.

In this exhibition, religious associations of vessels for holding water are also evoked. In Louise Manifold's *Visitors*, a small fountain is ringed by a fast decaying funerary wreath which comes apart in clumps of petals, twigs and leaves. Positioned at the side of the outside structures, the artwork seemed to me to take the place of a font in the outdoor cathedral, offering holy water to congregants and blessing the fingertips of the generations of ancestors inscribed in the empty landscape. Depopulation from loss during the Great Famine and 'clearances', was seized upon by commercial opportunism in the area.

*those missing tenants had abandoned their holdings to crowd into the workhouses or the emigrant ships to the New World, or they were dead; in any case they no longer infested the ground, which was left as a blank canvas on which Capital could paint a fair and profitable landscape*¹⁰.

Figure 3: At the base of a fountain, a detail of flowers in the work by Manifold (Image by Brent Meistre, Connemara, 2021)

To those familiar with the salmon hatchery when it was in operation, the word 'broken' evokes concerns about the preservation of the natural environment that were voiced at the time, and how chemicals and pigments leaked and polluted the waters and soil of the area¹¹.

Metaphysical invocations of broken vessels are many and ancient. For example, in the Jewish *midrash* which conceptualized the questions of diversity, agency and responsibility¹² by an allegory of (divine) unity being dispersed as light for human agents to collect and protect. The repair of broken crockery in *kintsugo* is physical celebration and expression of the Japanese philosophy of *mushin* ('no mind'), of an acceptance of change, fate and time to which all life is susceptible and subject¹³. Such notions were alluded to by the curator during an exhibition walkabout,

*key is the re-assembly or putting back together of that which shattered or broken to create a new thing unintentional beauty. So built into this thinking is that we can rebuild it or reconstitute. Also then if we break it, maybe we can remake, remake ourselves. It has a revolutionary edge to it.*¹⁴

The philosophical-material impulse is to conscientise the audience to actively seek the gaps, deviations and discrepancies which slip through the taken-for-granted cracks in dominant thinking, discourses and attention¹⁵. After historical trauma, the breaking of vessels is an allegorical and sometimes actual process of confronting and reckoning with the past. This is, firstly, to bear witness to loss and trauma of which no representation can be commensurate. It is also to enable counter-

narratives to historical progress to emerge, in the hopes of breaking the continuity of dominant historical interests in the present and future¹⁶. I have noted this drive emerging in post-Holocaust and post-apartheid art, describing how artmaking processes that are grounded in a ‘historical melancholia’ have agential energies awake to the dialectics of history, myth and imagination.

In this exhibition, the artistic works emerge not only from melancholia but also despair. Devastation has been wrought on humans by humans, as the historical destruction of European Enlightenment revealed of the capacity of human agency to dominate and oppress in contexts across the globe; and environmental violence has been enacted on non-human animals, where those not deemed useful for domestication have been seen as expendable and been driven to extinction. This hierarchy of disregard has extended to the extraction and abuse of the land, its plants and materials, the sea and the sky; and increasingly, beyond the earth into the far reaches of the planetary realm.

Entangled within the artists’ historical melancholia is environmental melancholia¹⁷. Across the artworks, writ large in both accusation and lamentation, are the all-encompassing past and future devastations which neither the artists nor we as viewers can escape, and about which we have trouble comprehending. Visualized aesthetically through gaps and fissures, the exhibition exposes the im-possibilities of confronting with such current and historical trauma, for the purpose of emphasizing “that the responsibility to remember and commemorate is that of the ethical viewer, whose memory must remain active and critical to the forces of the past in the present”¹⁶.

Part II

Figure 4: A viewer and signage at the entrance to the building of the Broken Vessel exhibition (Image by Brent Mestre, Connemara, 2021)

Walking an exhibition of 'heritage and mirage'

Broken Vessels was conceived as “a pilot exhibition project for a long-term art biennial”³ of collaborative creative arts projects between Irish and African artists. For the inaugural exhibition, which ran from the 14th September to the 15th October 2021, a small group of six artists were selected to engage with the curatorial thematics, the installation site and western Ireland. Three were artists working within the immediate local spaces and concerns, Anne Marie Daecy, Noelle Gallagher and Louise Manifold; and three worked remotely, based in South Africa, Christine Dixie, Monique Pelser and Lesego Rampolokeng.

The exhibition was curated by the South African artist Brent Mestre, curator of *Analogue Eye: Video Art Africa*, as part of the *Interface* programmes directed by Alannah Robins and produced by Jill Murray. The curatorial intention was for three features of the collaboration to align with the vision of *Analogue Eye*. Firstly, to engage audiences dialogically with the problematics of the time; secondly, in their materiality or intertextuality the artworks would “consider the sequential or repetitive, or the mechanics of the moving image, sound and text in relation to lens-based art”³; thirdly, the project would “take urban art works to rural areas” and rural audiences for site-specific interaction¹⁴.

The inaugural biennale was held purposefully on a rural site known for hosting a number of innovative scientific and creative arts research projects run by the The Inagh Valley Trust. This has included *Interface*¹⁸ an artist’s studio and residency program for artists, writers, performers and musicians run by Alannah Robins, with which the curator of this exhibition, Brent Mestre, had engaged in 2018¹⁹. This region of Ireland has retained traditional Irish culture, most notably through its language reclamation Connacht Irish-speaking *Gaeltacht* communities. The landscape, mostly treeless for the past 1000 years²⁰, has seen vast changes due to human impact, including recent controversial afforestation. The site and structures were consciously constructed by the curator as

*encapsulate[ing] and harbour[ing] indexes, traces and signifiers of the broken vessel. In its current state of re-assembly and re-imaging it from its former site as ‘construction’ or ‘assimilation of nature’, a harvesting of ova, milking, hatchings, fingerlings nurtured and cared for by hand and machine, artists are invited to intervene, adopt and re-animate the space and its resonances.*³

In the late 1980s, an inland salmon hatchery facility had been established in that forested area of the Inagh Valley, which sits in the remote area of Connemara in Ireland. Built by Ireland’s oldest cigarette company, Carroll’s, the project attracted much attention because of its ambitious scientific innovation in fish farming, its economic promise of rural investment, and the modernist aesthetic of the facility designed by Irish architectural practice of Scott Tallon Walker, which received awards nationally²¹. Now defunct, the hatchery project ultimately collapsed - a minor design flaw which necessitated pumping water against gravity to nurture the salmon hatchlings, added unsustainable economic costs²².

Surrounded by a forest of exotic trees, the lough at one end with distant sheep-dotted hills, and a rough track to the main road, the site is dominated by the rectangular building of the hatchery. Within it, various size rooms are cordoned off for various current purposes. These include a large gallery which has retained the name of its previous purpose, The Egg Room, connected to a smaller gallery, inter-leading doors, a large freezer and pieces of machinery. Detritus from the hatchery litters the surrounding outside areas. Two large, elevated box-shaped water towers stand at the edges, with metal staircases which one can climb to access the high algae-green landings. Green fiberglass water tanks dot the site, round in shape and uncovered, most have weeds, mushrooms and saplings growing within and around them. Deep rumbles are emitted from the two concrete, steel-roofed underground water reservoirs when one passes above, on ground level. These sounds, spaces and detritus provided a number of potential installation sites³, from which to catalyze the audience’s engagement.

Unlike a film festival where viewers are often passive participants, The Connemara Biennale seeks to be far more experiential in nature with viewers moving across the site and between works. Unlike a gallery or movie theatre,

dialogue, interchange, exchange between during and after the experience of the work is facilitated through the curatorial strategy of 'walking the site'.³

In the section of the essay which follows, I discuss the artworks in the order to the exhibition which the viewer would experience, when directed across the site by the exhibition map. I provide descriptions and include information provided by the artists and curator.

Shortly before sunrise, the spirits of the night dance their last dance

Driving up to the site, which is so remote it is not accessible by public transport or on foot from the nearest village, vehicles cross an open farm gate to enter the sitka forest. Alongside the track is a large white sign on which is printed the black and white dots and lines of a large QR code. Those who chose to alight, take out their mobile phones and scan the code, will see on the screen a bird, hunting.

*The apex predator, raptor, golden eagle, drone. Circling and surveying. **Entre Chein et Loup**, the witching hour between the known and unknown, a shifting in consciousness between the real and imagined.²³*

A few hundred meters down the track, on the side of a parked transport container are pasted sheets of white paper with the messy sketched profiles of the predator in flight (Figure 1).

Amongst the pines a container, reams and dreams of latent paper, offices and work places, forests shipped, traded and exchange. Inkjet, laserjet and retina displays, murmurations of birds of prey.²³

Enacted at different places across the site, Monique Pelsers' digital artworks visualise this apex, avian predator. Some of the artworks come into being only with the direct interaction of individual audience members, who conjure the animal when scanning a QR code, but only through the windows of the devices in their palms. A sleight of hand.

Pelser was interested in assertions of the belief and magic of photography which find (im)material form in the virtual pieces. This was informed by David Levi Strauss' ideas about magic and belief in photography²⁴, where the camera is thought of as "the first black box (vessel) of cybernetics"²⁵. The supernatural quality of imagery, accessible only through technological intervention, is palpable in her QR code works. The artist explained that she had been looking at the search-engine informed artworks of the US artist Penelope Umbrico; however unlike the endless excess of images accessible to that artist's appropriation, Pelser found one single source on the platform she was using: "It worked out well that the only raptor on Google 3d animals was the Golden Eagle, which then became emblematic of the USA and the smart phone"²⁵. This single animal of Northern Hemisphere falconry is appropriate for a neoliberal world obsessed with icons and the individual consumer object, from plastic water bottles to disposable Marvel superheroes. Of interest to the dialectic of art-science-nature of the site, is that this specific bird was attributed mystical value by many ancient cultures, in addition to being one of the most studied of the raptors by western science.

Figure 5: The container at the entrance to the site, with pasted drawings by Pelser (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

Figure 6: A detail of Pelsler's drawings of birds in flight pasted on the container (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

Two of the works transpose the digital to the analogue, where processes of technological reproduction and natural weathering erode the original visual to the point of disappearance and decay. In one, the artist's sketches of the predator in flight is pasted on the container, this erasure is enacted through exposure to the wet Connemara climate (Figure 2). The moisture and rain hydrate the wheaten glue and the pulp of the mass-produced paper, with ripples and curls forming under the sheets, as the container's metal skin constricts and expands in response to fluctuations of temperature in the late summer sun. In another, the erasure is a sign

of the limitations of human technological reproduction. As inkjet prints of the silhouette of a bird flies across the many realms of white paper, the colour gradually morphs from black precision into salmon pink smudges.

... 500 inkjet prints made with one ink cartridge (the vessel that runs out) on a desktop printer. Speaking to endless supply and the notion of perfection. There is a limitation in the process. 500 sheets of paper in a ream, one colour and one black and white ink cartridge and the same image is printed and the results are left to destiny. This is working the mechanical object and administration and office aesthetic²⁶.

Alongside the once 'Egg Room' of the hatchery, these reams of paper are stacked and spread on unpainted pine shelves. Minimalist artworks in their aesthetics, materiality and the immaterial became explicit. In the walkabout, the curator emphasized "the container, the office wares, office furniture and the shelf used here. Departure, relocation, migration, packaging preparing for distribution"¹⁴. Mortality emerges as a concern, as does the limitations of human determination. Pelsler wrote that she has already been exploring her fascination with "being stuck, as a limited human, in analogue as the world starts to move to digital" in prior works. The literal physical restrictions during the Covid-19 pandemic revealed the extremes of this in mundane minutia.

The idea of decay and erasure or becoming undone, exposed to the elements and fading is key to the work. It is echoed in these inkjet works. When the ink runs out you are not in control and the printed does random actions. Here the black became magenta or pink-like salmon. This element of control, between two worlds of the known and unknown is key.¹⁴

Pelser was interested in the impact of digital technology on both human and natural worlds. She wrote to me about her awareness that

the population of animals is dwindling so images and archives are increasing. I started to think about this during a crit session with one of my students who was photographing endangered fish species that are over fished in the oceans around Cape Town. With the digital file she can print that image/ simulacrum ad nauseum but the actual fish is in danger. I am curious how this affects our psyche.

This emerged in the artmaking process and later in her disembodied experience of the exhibition.

I feel very detached from it and unable to relate to it as a whole experience. I have only experienced it in snippets.... when I saw the footage of the tank with the QR code on it, it struck me that I had made nothing.²⁵

Figure 7: Discoloured ink prints of Pelser's birds in flight on the wooden shelving within the entrance to the exhibition (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

Leaving no footprint behind is an ecological ethic upheld in land art. The lack of travel by the international artists lessened the carbon footprint of the event. However, the digital footprint and the digital gaze persist visualized in the raptor's behavior as "the all seeing eye, the surveyor, the America golden eagle, but by extension a military drone and surveillance"¹⁴. Pelser's imaginings of the site were informed by the written descriptions and photographs provided by the curator and Irish artists, "displaced by current circumstances I viewed the land and site through a telephone camera, emailed visual data and instructions for the work to be made remotely"²⁷. Talking of the artmaking process, Pelser shared that

The experience to make work remotely was weird yet exciting. Responding to a place through a phone camera controlled by the person showing me the site was perfectly in line with my interests around photography and power relations... This mediated experience informed the work, which is about surveillance and the movement of information. And, furthermore, informed how the virtual reality video would be viewed; the viewer accessing a qr code with their camera phone which then directed them to a video piece.²⁵

The predator's cry extends across time and space from Ireland to South Africa, enabled through vortexes created by digital communication. "Listening to the sound on your device, you become a remote of the bird cries. Both the bird and the sound are simulacra drawn from the archive"²⁷. Pelser titled the work as a direct homage to the sound artist Chris Watson²⁸, perhaps most known for this work on the nature films of David Attenborough and the BBC. In his work of the same name, the relation to the before, during and after the rising of the sun "draw[s] horizontal and vertical axes through the historical strata past and present"²⁹ of different geographical contexts which are connected through sound. Sound is a material utilized in a number of the works in this exhibition, through which is viewer is called to be present.

A sense of covert activity led Pelser to position one of the artworks in the air above an underground tank outside of the hatchery building, framed by a vista of distant mountains and the stillness of the lough (Figure 3).

*The space reminded me of Simonstown in South Africa, seemingly untouched magnificent natural environment, home to South Africa's military base where the submarines and bunkers are. It has a surreal feeling to it because you sense the dual purpose. Like something is happening under the surface.*²⁵

Figure 8: A detail of the digital sceptre of a bird in flight visible on the screen of a mobile phone, laid down against the surface of a tank on the site (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

Slippages in duality, between the known and covert, analogue and virtual, are present in each of her works for this exhibition. The title is not only a reference to certain conditions of transition from day to light, but also to the medium of “photography and belief and disbelief/ document as truthful evidence”. In referring to the supernatural, virtual predators and traces of life lived elsewhere, she brings forth the viewers’ critical consciousness of non-capturable aspects of what is occurring around us.

Walking from the vanishing silhouettes of this predator on the paper realms to one’s right in the first gallery, the viewer then turns into the darkened Egg Room.

In the absence of air

Placed deep within, on an angled rectangular screen, is the video piece by Louise Manifold. The title correctly describes the claustrophobic “shadowy unsettled atmosphere” of both the room and the flickering projection of her telling of a “dystopian myth and forest fable”, where “synthetic and real coexist” in a forest clearing³⁰.

*Leaves fall ashen like black turf. Hollowed legs static, synthetic against the real, form a headless and breathless figure disorientated in stray sod. A shroud, The Morrigan, the phantom queen, foretelling the destruction and the fate of war, of humans and land, a future uncertain. She comes as a crow, in the air, in dark clouds.*²³

The mythical character of The Morrigan is one entangled with the literary psyche of Ireland.

*Her aspect changes from tale to tale. She appears sometimes as a triple goddess and sometimes as a solitary one, sometimes as a beautiful girl, or as a powerful woman in her prime, and other times as a hag. She may be a goddess of battle, who takes the shape of a raven or carrion crow. She can foretell and bring about victory for an army, or for a particular hero. She is an earth goddess connected with the fertility of the land and the procreation of cattle. She is also a goddess of great sexual powers, who sleeps with the chief god or hero, thus ensuring his victory in war.*³¹

Associations formed by Irish translations of the *lamia* in the Vulgate (Isiah 34.14), of a child-devouring monster living among graveyard corpses, fed into the Morrigan as an ominous female creature associated with desolation and death³¹.

Depending on the text or the teller, the Morrigan may be portrayed as prophetess, shape-shifting war goddess or fertility goddess. Yet in this work, she appears disembodied. Without torso to morph into the wings of a crow, she can no longer fly to frighten or to inspire those battle. The forest around her has devastated the indigenous ecology, because “as the trees move in, silence falls across the land. No birds sing, no bees buzz, no flowers bloom”³². Without a womb, she cannot engage in pleasure nor generate anew. Only stunted legs remain, stiff vertical lines in parallel to the trunks which surround them.

The artist’s interests were in The Morrigan’s visions of a destruction on earth, which extended to how she represented the landscape and figurative elements³³. Unintentionally echoing the variations in the telling of this myth, in the video sometimes a single pair of legs appears, at other times all three appearances of the Morrigan appear. In another artwork produced for the exhibition *Air Looms* the year before, Manifold had also engaged again with bodies, their parts and destruction. Evocatively recalled by Rainsford, when writing on that show, they appeared as “A trio of atomized dolls made between 1786 and 1774/ A reanimated corpse written into existence in 1818/ A beloved heart salvaged in 1822”³⁴. In this exhibition, the spectral figure parts are sometimes shrouded by a cloth.

*The hollow legs in my video are the broken vessels for me, they become/ or take on human form when covered but are still absent and hollow beneath their covering.*³⁵

Forming an awkward triangle where a neck or shoulder would be, if the figure were anatomically correct, in this video piece the form seems not of human invention, but it is stunted, otherworldly.

The video piece itself is shrouded: at the beginning and end, a white cloth fills the screen; at times it obscures and at other times merges with the over-exposed, misted changes to the cataclysmic scene. Ash falls in unnatural ways from an oppressive sky, like black snow onto a stage set in a clearing of felled wood against bleached trees. The scene triggers a memory from over two decades ago: of finding the grave of Sarie Mare³⁶, of the Afrikaans folk song *Sarie Marais*, in Kwazulu-Natal of South Africa, forgotten in the midst of the wide, muddy tracks of logging machinery.

Figure 9: Details of the figure within Manifold’s projection (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

For Manifold, the landscapes of Connemara are familiar subjects of both her domicile and of her artmaking.

*I see Connemara as a very multifaceted site, one site the north west side where the interface is located is extremely beautiful in the traditional sense of Irish landscapes, whilst the south west coast of Connemara is much more desolate and parched, but equally beautiful.*³⁵

Despite such familiarity, the artist has expressed that “there is often a feeling of both exile and refuge, depending on your life position”³⁵. She had attempted to bring this dissonance to the artworks from its very inception. In personal correspondences, she shared that at first she was interested in the literary and intellectual outsiders to the region, naming specifically Ludwig Wittgenstein, Virginia Wolfe and Sylvia Plath, whose visits had involved mending or reflection on the broken. The relationship of the American Plath and her English partner, Ted Hughes, fell apart when travelling the area, as outlined in a book Manifold has been reading - *Red Comet: The Short Life and Blazing Art of Sylvia Plath* by Heather Clark. She initially envisaged “creating a video work as a meditation on the landscape as a refuge for people and broken circumstances in their lives”³⁵. Both intimate and specific, but also endemically historic to the sense of place, she then “walked the famine trail” which connects Mayo and Galway³⁵. When walking alone, the artist then “came across a particular barren location on my walks on the Glann road, where a number of trees had been cleared” which recalled a photograph by the artist Gillian Wearing. Instead of her original intentions, she chose “to leave influences and sentiment behind and work with my intuition, and make a commitment to a location as a site to shoot”³⁵.

In my reading and discussion with the artists about the intentionality of these works, I found a number of echoes of thinking running across them. One of these link the two Irish artists (Manifold, Gallagher) whose work the viewer would encounter one after the other. That is, local mythologies of luck or changes in fortune, as ways in which to negotiate what one has trouble understanding about inequality, injustice, time and destruction. Justification is placed as inexplicably beyond the realm of human creation. Manifold alluded to this “disorientation”³⁰ in present conditions, to a local superstition, where even those familiar to a place may, literally and inexplicably, be unsettled by unearthing the ground beneath their feet.

*I was really interested in the myth of turning the stray sod. whereby a solitary traveller at night will inadvertently step on a stray sod, and no matter how good their sense of direction, they immediately lose their path.*³⁵

For an unfamiliar listener such as myself, this may sound like a warning to leave what is hidden or buried ‘well enough alone’ being careful of missteps. Manifold was indeed interested in how the work might express the “anxiety” of floundering solutions in the face of devastation. The commonplace story refers to ill-fortune and even insanity³⁷. The charm lies in undoing the natural order of things by wearing one’s coat inside out, as undertaken by the blanketed figures in the videopiece. Through practices inverted, one finds one’s way through the madness of prevailing conditions.

Emerging from the darkened Egg Room into the light of the adjoining gallery, a piece of machinery squats beneath the title of the next artwork.

Fortune’s Wheel

The exhibition guide introduces this series of painting by Noelle Gallagher in reference to the medieval philosophical *Rota Fortunae*. An ancient Greek interpretation of the zodiac, the unpredictable nature of windfalls and misfortune are attributed to a device. Gallagher was initially drawn to visual interpretations of this myth when studying Classics, describing that

*I loved these images of kings tumbling from their thrones down to the earth and stored them away in my mind’s eye for future use. I thought of them again when visiting the hatchery; how the attempt to control nature had failed, industry now found itself at the bottom of the wheel and nature was reasserting itself at the top.*³⁸

The exhibition guide includes a quotation which places the blindfolded deity Fortune within a similar interpretation of mythical womanhood as that of Manifold’s.

*Dissembled, barren, emptied for light. “Break all the spokes and fellies from her wheel”.*²³

In the original Hamlet (2.2.495), the speaker was making a plea to a seemingly more fair Christian god for the world to be ordered by justice, constructing Fortune as a prostitute responsible for senseless killing. The quotation is set alongside adjectives of conditions devoid of the potential for regeneration or photosynthesis.

Figure 10: Details of the painting (left, middle) and projection (right) of Gallagher (Images by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

While the Rota Fortunae myth concerned itself with the changes affecting private goods and gains, Gallagher recalls it to bring attention to losses to the common good where “the wheel of industrial progress and hope [are] disassembled”³. In her paintings, sitka trees blur, objects disappear and the canvas scratches back at the mark making. The struggle with structure, in the content she represents and on the painterly surface itself, points to the murky problematics of profits and costs from quick fix unsustainable solutions, including that of fish farming and afforestation³⁹. At the root of the local viewers’ experience, she creates an attraction-repulsion experience of the Inagh Valley, acting as a mediator of their affective morality.

*I feel an ambivalence towards the site, a deep attraction to the strong verticals of the Sitka trees, and the broken horizontals of an abandoned shipping container, while also repulsed by what they represent. How can I be drawn to these barren clearfelled areas that open up areas to the light - when they don't provide any cover for other living beings?*⁴⁰

Gallagher explained that, while making this series, she had joined an ecoactivism group “where I learned about concepts such as the *symbioscene*, where we work with the planet to our mutual benefit rather than placing ourselves at the centre”³⁸. There are no human figures in her work. Rather, spectres of non-human animals and beings gaze back⁴¹, but without defiance and little hope. In her painterly negotiations with the natural and man-made features of the site, the retinal imprint of a deer in *Clearfelled* is all that is left of her artistic processes of reckoning with the contestations of this indigenous species to exist⁴² in balance with the requirements of responsible conservation management⁴³.

Deer sightings book-ended my visits to Interface. Stags featured heavily in my earlier (unresolved) paintings for Broken Vessels. I also made a screenprint that featured a stag.

Once more stable than cycles of fortune, the annual regeneration of deers’ antlers became associated, in Irish mythology,⁴⁴ with forest ecology and the potential of creativity, security and power. The resultant painting conceived of such hopes as precarious. Gallagher writes that “if we wish for re-integration between humans and the rest of nature we will not call for a cull of native species but find other solutions” which “eschew the great chain of being”, a western mythology of hierarchy which enabled the age of dominance of the Anthropocene. The sky overlays the outlined absences of trees, and thin washes of pithy beige soil bleach the once dense umbers of peat. Painterly materiality is deployed in this series, as in others of her works, “to undermine the photographic elements” where “perspective is skewed to allude to how memory alters our sense of place”⁴⁵.

Gallagher was interested in how to convey the local’s “fugitive feelings, solastalgia and regret” when their distress at the environmental change around them is exacerbated by powerlessness and lack of control⁴⁶. She complicates their victimhood, by pointing to their memories of collusion with myths of commerce, progress towards an industrial future bought with “terrible consequences for the environment”³⁸. The affective turn towards “guilt and grief” differs from her assuredness to handle the uncertainty of artmaking.

Uncertainty and ambivalence are feelings that I've come to terms with in my practice - the built environment and the natural world are often presented side by side in my paintings, hard lines beside softer shapes, something fixed and defined beside something fluid, it's like I get a moment of clarity, then that certainty drifts away³⁸.

This sense of drift continues in the exhibition, reinforced in the next artwork the viewer encounters outside at the periphery of the field of tanks.

Visitors

Figure 11: Newly replaced flowers encircling the installed fountain, ahead of the exhibition opening night (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

The water fountain, infinite source, cyclical, stately symbol of power, wealth and order. A construction of nature. At the wake house, a wreath, a reservoir of tears.²³

Squirting from one of the small tanks is a tentative fountain ringed by fresh flowers in various states of decay. Tiny in relation to the pool of water which surrounds it, the erratic jet is a child's hand-made fancy aspiring to stateliness.

Historically fountains and water features were originally symbols of wealth order and power. The endless continuous flowing, represents the eternal nature of this mystical dimension and also the infinite nature of its source. The pond is an intervention which allows us to see this body of water as something that is governed by our desire to place order in the natural environment.³⁰

The floral ring holds the viewer's gaze, jiggling as it threatens to unravel across the surface. This is not a solemn commemorative wreaths of the type that cements the triumphs of world wars across Europe; nor the funerary wreaths commercialised for placement on coffins or graves. Seemingly composed of wild meadow flowers interwoven haphazardly by the artist's hand, it is an intimate object made to disentangle and disintegrate with time. The production was "a very immediate response"³⁵ which differed to the labour and longevity of *In the absence of air*. The materiality of the site was centered in this piece.

I loved that the tank was full of stagnant old water, which made it feel quite melancholic with the flower petals moving around.

In one of Manifold's prior artworks about western Ireland, she had explored the *passage* through water of drift seeds, as subjectivities of migration and mortality. Writing about her fascination with small, anonymous botanical artefacts in *On Seaside Surrealism*, she explained,

Natural phenomena have a way of connecting to one's own subjective impulse.... I felt sea fruits explain the landscape that they have washed up on – marooned in Connemara where everything looks a little stranded. They become both the embodiment and abstraction of these surroundings: like unexpected arrivals to a landscape marked by histories of departure... they are true objects of anxiety, cast by a history of accidents, to mirror one's own sense of displacement in the world.⁴⁷

As the wreath uncoils itself across the water vessel, such mirroring becomes a playful, irreverent foil to the nearby procession of veils in the colour of mourning. The viewers encounter these next in their journey, careful not to trip or overturn the unpredictable terrain underfoot.

Blueprint for the Disorder of Things, Blueprint for a Breathless World

Figure 12: An installation view showing the veil-like translucency of the material of the prints by Dixie (Image by Brent Arthur Mestre, Connemara, 2021)

Intended originally to feature side-by-side around one of the medium tanks, as if enlarged cinematic stills of a zoetrope⁴⁸, the eight prints of Christine Dixie are installed from rectangular metal frames flapping in the wind. Against natural and technological features of the outside world, is the artwork's bookishness. The title references Michael Foucault's book *The*

Order of Things “as a way of unraveling the text in relation to this time in history”¹⁴. Words from that text feature within the series, with the panels too appearing as if pages in a book arranged in a narrative sequence. The flow however is not as smooth as the water furrow over which the veils flutter because, as the artist describes,

What I was interested in was that when the pandemic first started, I felt as if I couldn't concentrate on reading. Everything seemed very disconnected and words and meanings seemed to me disconnected. So the idea of language itself being somehow disrupted was something I became interested in. And also I don't know if you know Laurie Anderson's song Language is a virus? I kind of liked that idea of language itself being viral.⁴⁸

On the translucent, veil-like prints are printed the pages of a book with words, featureless landscapes and figures.

In a breathless world, three characters interact and infect each other. The 'princess', from Velasquez's Las Meninas, The plague doctor and a dog. The landscape rises and falls. The 'hand of god' sprays.

These are framed with diminutive figures of costumed humans and animals, including the fish type specific to the hatchery.

Spacecraft and astronauts float with oxygen tanks and aqualungs. Salmon migrate breathing through spring and salt water.²³

Developed during the hard lockdown period from the etching plates produced for a prior video project *To Be King* (2014) video project, Dixie created the artist's book *Blueprint for the disorder of things* in collaboration with bookbinder Helene van Aswegen, from which pages were adapted into the veils⁴⁸ of the same name and the video piece *Blueprint for a Breathless world*.

The colour of Indigo, the colour used for a 'blueprint' permeates this book. The architectural references associated with a blueprint - a means by which architects draw out 'a plan for the future' becomes paradoxical in the context of disorder. The long association of indigo with trade-routes alludes to the routes by which The Black Plague and the current pandemic have been spread.⁴⁹

One of the first series that appears in the book, which then features in the treatment of landscape in the veils, was titled *The Disorder Trade off*. The work was her exploration of the tradeoffs between economic activity and human health during the pandemic, which countries across the globe were “trying to balance”⁴⁸ the trade versus not getting the plague. She described how

One of the things I became quite interested in with where all these diagrams of rates of infection and different countries having the spikes at different points in the year. That kind of tracking and diagrammatic images that have been shown to us a lot [during COVID-19]. So I use these as kind of mountainscapes in the background.⁴⁸

On the veils where such landscape features, are included the infection rate, continent and time of year of the spike in infection. The curator alluded to this morphing of infection rate statistics in his walkabout, describing how “landscape rises and falls like graphs, the Kompasberg, lateral lines salmon use to sense magnetic north. Distance”.¹⁴ Kompasberg (literally ‘compass mountain’) has featured in much of Dixie's work, as the recognizable mountain silhouette visible from the village of the outsider-artist Helen Martin. When referred to in relation to distance, biology and the salmon's instinctual journey to reproduction and to death, it functions to connect drives of instinct and magnetism to migrations across desolate, inhospitable, transcendent spaces.

Figure 13: Details of the different installation views of Dixie's three figures, from the front in overcast light (right), billowing in the sunshine through the back of the fabric, and reflected in the water below (Image 1 by Brent Meistre, Image 2 and 3 by Dina Zoe Belluigi, all Connemara, 2021)

The human characters, The Princess and The Plague Doctor, seem to paint themselves in and out of being as queens, artists, creators, biological renditions and medicalized body parts. They have been present before in the artist's oeuvre, as the curator explained,

Working with the Velasquez's Las Meninas as a reference point for the past few years, she has woven her own personal family history into a wider contemporary South Africa society. Much of this has been focussed around mapping of the woman's body, violence and masculinity, power and how that is transposed onto the landscape. Often using her children as subjects in the works as we see her daughter Rosalie resembled here with her dog who recently passed.¹⁴

Using a talk-aloud protocol, the artist shared her development of the figures that feature within the *Blueprint* artworks, where "slowly some things happened" in the studio between the many figures she was "playing around with before the pandemic".

The Plague Doctor figure came out of a figure that I'd done before the pandemic. And it was a combination of The Princess, but it also had an African mask over the face, and then medical instruments embedded into the mask. And this figure was the opposite of the Princess who holds the paintbrush.⁴⁸

An African mask with similar features to the Igbo White Spirit Maiden Mask forms the basis of the head and headdress⁵⁰ of the Plague Doctor figure, with the rounded shapes on the headdress enlarged into spikes, tufts or flows of ink blown over a page. Over these Dixie sketched masks collected from her time at the Venice Biennale in 2017, including one with pustules marking plague infection and a beaked mask which had intrigued her because of the supposedly preventative herbs held therein. Within the artist's book, the two figures move about, interact and slowly merge as if The Princess and the Plague Doctor are "actually part of one another, that they weren't separate. It's like almost accepting the bad inside oneself"⁴⁸. However, in the series for this exhibition, we see the aftermath of what happens when the two figures meet, the Plague Doctor Figure dominates, and the Princess figure ultimately floats away.

On one of the arms of the metal frames which hold the flapping prints, is a small inconspicuous QR-code. An 'easter egg', in video game terminology, hidden in plain sight for the most attentive of viewers, it opens a video collaboration between Dixie and South African multimedia artist Mark Wilby, *Blueprint for a Breathless World*. As each page turns, fades, blurs or is panned across, elements are elegiacally animated against midnight darkness. Planets spin, a pack of dogs bows in submission to their leader, figures disappear and flicker against one another. The music involves contrasts: the gentle leitmotif of wind instruments intercepted by the guttural overtone (*umngqokolo* or throat singing) of Xhosa women⁵¹ singing the piece *Nomaweza*; the rising and falling rasps of hospital breathing apparatus with beeps of a heart machine; monastic humming and organ tomes before the static white noise. The experience as a listen mirrors the experience of the sound artist Karen Cooper who composed the work, when she undertook the artistic research process for her postdoctoral ethnomusicology study:

As my ears grew accustomed to the sound world I heard additional counter melodies.⁵²

The videopiece ends when the Plague Doctor, arm upraised and painting, and the large quarter moon fades, leaving the outline of the ashen book which began the sequence, barely traceable against the blackened ground.

Walking a bit further down the furrowed aisle, the translucent veils reveal and obscure the objects and trees which surround them, directing one closer to the voice emanating from deeper into the forest clearing.

Bush Radio

Figure 14: A detail of the installation of the spoken poem by Rampolokeng (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

Spindly metal coat hangers hand-shaped into aeriels reach out above four diminutive radios, placed on piles of logs stacked neatly under a water tower. The smallness of this still life scene is unexpected, pathetic. Even at this proximity, the voice of Lesego Rampolokeng which is transmitted from the plastic boxes all too easily catches on, echoes and merges with the more immediate noises of the creaking wood and contracting metal about the place. With intent listening, body poised, fragments of poems become decipherable, just as the voice disappears, before another fragment emerges. An atlas of lost transmissions.

His connecting of words are very visual, often creating scenarios, caricatures of time, often violent, abject, satirical and subversive, that often acted upon us as the listener and re-inagined in our minds.¹⁴

As the hues and accents of imagery change and clash in his poetry, the surrounding area transforms itself. The field of the circular tanks and logged trunks become “multiple Satin rings across limbo-land sliding into the bog”. Religious and scientific association blur as legitimised systems of power’s abuse in phrases such as “putrescent hymns” and “righteous schemers blasphemous remade”. His “exposure of the church’s contradictions and hypocrisy”⁵³ and its amnesias would resonate with Irish audience members as much as African. Imagery of trauma, loss and deceit at a mass scale is intertwined with supremacy and colonialism. The abuse and self-interest of those at the top (“priest is Narcassist”; “your preacher’s vestments/ a murder investment”; “head-severance for religious retirement”) extend to the foot soldiers. The KKK are exposed as “God’s handymen/ minions in Diabolo’s playpen/ Hell hawk soldiers of the kindergarten/ fantasized dominion over creation”. At other points, behavioural descriptions bring the empirical home, relating human conditions to human actions⁵⁴.

how they pray before they slay innocence.
*Revillers defilers moral amputees arm stumped.*¹

Included is the hypocrisy of Western educational myths (“civilize what? enlighten whom?”), institutions (“the shame academy”) and elites (“minds gone on intellectual fashion trips”) that continue to collude with inequitable systems (“to ingest and regurgitate into the drool school of the Nation state”). Underpinning this, is the concern with the effects of the reproductions of such systems of power.

In pedagogy of subjugation
Atomic waste matter
*Brain/senses clogged up to irrelevance*⁵⁴

In the walkabout, the curator offered the interpretation that the poet was utilising “thoughts, rants and rhymes to navigate his own head space through isolation, struggles, black consciousness, traumatic and colonial histories”.¹⁴ While there are intimations of such internal reflection, there is a blurring of certainty as to the subject being addressed. In the exhibition map prompt, the intended audience is clear.

First there was the word, in the airwaves. In exile, a revolutionary, a freedom fighter, a pirate, a poet.
*Broadcasting from afar to the surveyed black body, preyed upon, refusing to be colonized.*²³

At times, it is as if the narrator is indeed speaking to African listeners. In asides, cautions are expressed to listeners whose legacies involved subjugation,

(forgive the unrepentant & you fit their definition of you:
*yours the sub-human species’ view)*⁵⁵

Pronouns sometimes create binary positions.

They played
*While we prayed*⁵⁵

In such juxtapositions, he constructs what has been described as “a Janus-faced temporal structure that allows for the past to partly obscure the present and to insert the traumatic experience of violence”⁵⁴. Such devices function as “metaphors for erasure”⁵⁴ within these counter-stories of history. Since he does not identify those he addresses (“buttercup”) or accused (“snitches for god”), we are somewhat implicated in such violence. At points, the listener is positioned as part of the whiteness of bystanders (“rosy sight seers”), or possibly it is a reference “to the artists about this collaboration, about holding our lily white hands”, as the curator has suggested.¹⁴ Of little doubt is the confrontation of systems of objectification within western spectacles of observing and archiving.

Ancestors human zoos to modern day seed

museum pieces voyeuristic exhibition¹

Appropriate to the site, references to the insatiable western scientific gaze permeate the fragments. This is poignantly stated in the line “object study subject me”. In a number of the passages, Rampolokeng contrasts the dispassionate stultifying control of scientific rationality against the exotic spectacle of suspended death of the taxidermist.

formaldehyde promises the nation's hide to embalm

still transition phase space between butchery and mortuary⁵⁴

In the name of scientific discovery, curiosity and trophies for western audiences, parts of human and wild animals from the so-called ‘new world’ have been preserved in such ways and displayed. The notion that promises of the future may have that effect on an entire nation is powerfully disturbing. The eugenics theme repeats across the text, including references to the violence wrought on indigenous people. In one moment, for example, we hear the phrase “still label original human animal”, a reference to the treatment of the first nation of South Africa whose offer of “open arms of welcome” to Europeans (the “scurvied pale”) when they first arrived in the Cape, was met by those who “took greedy advantage” and enacted violence (“rape and pillage”) and later genocide⁵⁴. Such juxtaposition of complex, often contrasting imagery enables “irony and anger to blend”⁵⁶. In another fragment, “rally/ Raleigh calls for ‘savage native’ dissemination for peace”⁵⁵, ambiguity marries the term for urging troops to prepare themselves for war, with the imposed name of the first recorded North American Indian to be forcibly abducted to England⁵⁷. In both the references to trauma inflicted on indigenous people cited here, a direct link is made to the words coined in the West for the mass killing of animals and people: “Khoisan-extinction”; “Holocaust a concept European owned”.

By negating “the forms of abjection that are at the base of oppression”, Rampolokeng posits the “logical outgrowth of such a situation is a moral and political response”⁵⁴. However, here too there is no mirage for the listener. Instead, disappointment and disgust at political leadership repeats across the fragments.

Blind mice squeal for mass appeal.

Monstrosity experience in politics medley, evil political animals, medieval hot seats.¹

More than the few individuals (or “blind mice”), there is accusation of fundamental corruption of the systems of regulation and governance (“infantile tantrums legislated/ constitution incontinent”). References to apartheid and post-apartheid South African, English and French colonialism, early independence Africa, past and current English and US politics litter the fragments, where the failures and misdeeds of leadership sit alongside vulnerabilities.

Who needs who leads who feeds

faecal lies Tears diapers eye and ear wipers

must action yes

but flesh, cartilage, bone we all go home alone.¹

Rampolokeng’s observations of post-apartheid conflation of freedom with self-gratifying consumption, has been echoed by many scholars who have witnessed post-colonial independence and neoliberal logics, including that of Frantz Fanon⁵⁴. In his clustering of images, the complexity of the politics of development is revealed. Seeing through the falsehoods of benevolence, are the “grotesqueries”. Those whose “scruples” are surprisingly “the worst qualities”; where strategic commercialism offers the rich indulgences through “shame relief stores”; where the excess of capitalism lull complacency (“opulent tedium/ affluent boredom”; “cold, comatose in warm affluence”). In these conditions of capitalist exploitation, the surface tensions between political factions divert attention from corruption and the destruction wrought on living beings.

nutrients, genetic modified crops, fertilized

capital call for more mass murder.

Most poverty strapped major spender.

Right step up radioactivity.

Left locked in mystical exercise.

Head polluted orifice activity.¹

At certain moments, the frenzied rhythm of the poetry quietens, allowing for devastating conclusions to be made, and heard, about what continues underneath such spectacles.

Meanwhile back on the power range

nothing is strange.¹

In other moments, the strength of impending revolutionary resistance emanates from within the poet-figure, particularly in this repeated first-person phrase:

Riddim Rhyme Reason I'm primed

Ticking down to detonation⁵⁵

The artist does so, standing as witness surrounded by the destruction and subjugation of the living world. Such resistance, 'far from being merely a reaction to imperialism, is an alternative way of conceiving human history'⁵⁸. As some have suggested, this may perhaps be Walter Benjamin's notions of messianic time. Rupturing how time and history are narrated - without blind adherence to myths of progress on which the future is banked, but rather a present and past of very tangible material struggles for ethical fulfillment, where future revolution is narrowly possible⁵⁴. This is at a standpoint on the other side of the abyssal line⁵⁹, where questions of the human, the ecological, narratives of hope, are approached by neither acquiescing or sublimating such historical and environmental trauma, but by instigating resistance against the normalization of such a schema.⁵⁴

Rampolokeng's "poetics of disgust" disable any possible indifference of the listener⁵⁴.

waste as the product of a loss of meaningfulness... Waste, which offers nothing useful apart from its undesirability and capacity to raise disgust, is a useful poetic metaphor for Rampolokeng. It is precisely in its ability to dissociate us from the familiar that it challenges our standards of acceptance. This is what I think of as the poetics of disgust in his work.⁵⁴

Mkhize noticed how, in prior works of the poet's oeuvre, "violence and smell... function metonymically between the terrain of the literal and that of the existential".⁵⁴ In this exhibition, the installation of the poetry atlas as a site-specific installation transmitted over radio, shifts that relation to the sense of hearing. "The gamut of sounds the mouth can make in an often visceral, abject and violent manner"¹⁴ is employed for the viewer to hear the intimate cracks of limbs breaking and evil laughter emitted; the noises of devices that project and communicate information.

Neck break crack cackle

best voice box wolf speak

Aliment Tweet

Battle Cry or mongrel in the sewer canal

in the mouth and out the arse runs the barbed wire¹

Even with such Goya-like expressions of trauma, there is persistence, strength, in rare snippets of the poem.

broke, yes, never broken.

I strive beyond survived to live¹

This “auditory terrorism”, a phrase Rampolokeng repeats in various guises in *Bush Radio*, resonates with the objectives of one of the Irish artists in the show, Anne Marie Deacy, for whom sounding holds the hope of catalyzing human agency.

Eigentone: 126.22Hz - 221.23Hz

Installed in a non-space within the hatchery building, is the unobtrusive sound piece by Anne Marie Deacy. Walking into a passageway in the main building to find the work, the viewer encounters a long cupboard with drawers marked by labels of specimens, utensils and chemicals utilised long ago. Led by muffled sounds, one walks into a concrete room with pockmarked floors and dark terracotta walls. Three pristine sheets of corrugated steel stand vertically positioned in seemingly ad hoc configurations. Vibrating.

Figure 15: Installation view of the artwork by Deacy viewed from within the acoustic space (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

The weighty material was chosen to allude to its “imprint on the landscape, as rural architecture in Ireland but also the other uses this material has lent itself to in recent history, images of shelter, poverty and as home come to mind”⁶⁰.

*A roof, a shelter, an embodiment. Corrugations tuned to celestial bodies, frequencies of sun and moon. Helios and Luna. Healing hertz, vibrating and permeating the vessel.*²³

The steel sheets were intended to function as monuments which, when responding to the sound of field recordings of tuning forks, becoming membranes of frequencies which permeate the “the very cells of the body” and into space. The artist was thinking of such materiality of sound⁶¹ when making decisions about installation. Manipulating the psychoacoustics of the space, she carefully angled the suspension of each sheet in relation to each other, the walls, hidden electronics and the viewer, to prevent the dilution of “some of the magic and alchemy”⁶².

The sound was composed as a four channel piece and a four channel composition lasting 10 minutes and 23 seconds set to play on a loop.

*The beginning of the work, each sheet calling out alone, the end all sounding in unison. The importance to me was not, under the climate of the time, for people to stay to listen to a whole work, but to experience the vibrations and ebb and flow at their own will. There is something ritualistic about this aspect of repetition and using these alternate frequencies to create a work away from the western 12 tone construct to compose.*⁶²

The artist’s aesthetics of ‘deep listening’ and attentive ‘sonic awareness’⁶³ of one’s environment were in part inspired by the embodied “sonic mediations of Pauline Oliveros who viewed listening as activism and a belief that sound and sounding can stimulate change and transformation”⁶⁴. Seeking repair and recalibration at the scale of “a universal pain”⁶⁰, she writes that “we have been desensitised to the destruction that we are a part of. This work is an attempt to explore sound as a way of recalibrating a broken humanity”.⁶⁴ However, she emphasized that “even in the act of activating the tuning forks as they vibrated through me, I was interested in creating a work which explored recalibration by embracing the sounding of dissonance”⁶².

Through a written text at the venue, the viewer is provided an opening to the artists’ thinking about how this relates to specific sounds in her work, matched to the frequencies 126.22Hz - 221.23Hz.

*Using mathematician Hans Cousto's theory of The Cosmic Octave and his search for harmony, the recordings of the tuning forks incorporated into this four channel installation respond to the frequencies of the sun, moon and selected planets as they orbit the axis of the earth.*⁶⁴

In his modern take on the metaphysical quest for *musica universalis*, Cousto’s book on orbital resonance describes the development of the ‘cosmic octave’ through astronomically-based calculations. The text itself is presented as a means for readers to “discover more harmony in life by consciously tuning himself (sic) to harmonious cosmic rhythms” and tones which the author asserts have long been utilised within cultures ancient and primordial. In bringing these explicit connections together, Deacy seems to be engaging with questions about the contributions of western knowledge mythologies to modern eco-cosmology where environmental priorities are central to human well-being⁶⁵, by intertwining connections between sound and matter.

Deacy had, prior to the exhibition, already engaged with such notions of orbital resonance and also ‘sounding’ as a verb related to “listening as activism”⁶⁶. She had also made work in response to rural isolation and its exacerbation during the pandemic, and to the Interface site during a 2020 residency⁶⁷. She had shared insights with Pelsler about her *music for six smartphones*, where the “sound object / postcards” she created displayed a google map image of Interface on one side, as if from bird’s eye view, and QR codes on the other, for the viewer to access a score to be played collectively at a point in time⁶⁸. However, when reflecting about the experience of the *Broken Vessels* exhibition, Deacy wrote that “I had no comprehension when I first started to make this sound sculpture the profound effect that the whole experience would have on me”. The mentorship experience with the sound artist and educator Peter Flemming (Concordia University, Canada); the “undaunted belief” of the curator Brent Mestre; and the various dialogues she had with the South African artists during the project which were “incredibly enriching”⁶⁰, in particular the collaboration with Lesego Rampolekeng, led to what she described as “a growth spurt” in her artistic practice.

At the beginning of this essay, I recounted how Rampolokeng's voice a preacher-ancestor emanated from the emptied holy of holies across the field. Deacy's work, instead, was contained within an enclave of the new church of science, in almost all ways a very different presentation and sense of belief. Between the two, however, was the collaborative piece *Riddim Rhyme Reason*, comprised of echoes between the two, as if an attempt at 'call and response'.

The placement and echoes reminded me of an interactive educational display within Addo, a wildlife reserve in South Africa. Scientific explanations of frequencies and environmental influences on the reflection, refraction and absorption of elephant sounds⁶⁹ are included on an infographic to direct the viewer's education, much as Deacy's written narrative does, about how listening and sounding (as a verb) connects us, vocalises identity and experience, and bridges distance and difference. But visceral learning happens in the fleeting moment. A child takes a step into the giant arc of acrylic skull and ear, and as another person whispers into the other receptacle shape many meters away, she hears the mutterings with intimate clarity. The metal sheets of Deacy's work too dwarfed the viewer, much like the vertical flaps of an elephant's ear; though in this arrangement, the small exoskeletons of the Bush radios were more like ticks or dungbeetles than beasts. So across the field, the sound had become garbled, leaving only the frequencies for the viewer.

Riddim Rhyme reason

Occurring only once, lasting for less than an hour at the very end of the Ireland's nationwide Culture Night, was the interactive stereopiece collaboration between Anne Marie Deacy and Lesego Rampolekeng. A playful collective affair, into the setting sun boomed a transmission of Rampolokeng's spoken poem *Riddim Rhyme Reason*, as the 40 or so viewers responded with giggles to Deacy's unexpected invitation to take hold of tiny electronic devices and put them to their chests, against parts of the building and metal detritus sprawling about the site, to feel the vibrations and resonances moving through matter. Deacy had for a while before been exploring radio transmission as a form of community healing, influenced by Oliveros' work on the Sonosphere, and "the idea of the sounds transmitted having this invisible range and power"⁶². She wrote reflectively after the event that, "Lesego, while not there in person that night, his work was in the cell of everyone as his powerful words vibrated through the ether of Interface, with the small vibration of tuning forks punctuating the air".⁶⁰ At the end of the event, the artists apparently "shared a deep connection about how this process had really moved us"; however, the process leading to it had involved disequilibrium. Deacy explained that,

This was also the first time I was introduced to the powerful spoken word/ writings of Lesego Rampolokeng. When hearing his work for the first time, I am reminded by a line Dina you mentioned at Culture Night, that his work could be intense and it did not come with a trigger warning. No one is spared as Lesego shares his truth. I felt a bit of resistance at first, but then when reading over the words, this was the real deal, the daunting feeling also that I am part of the problem he speaks of. In reality we are all part of the problem but I seek to explore other possibilities through sound as a solution. With Lesego I was also given a small insight into some aspects of the current situation in South Africa. This all really impacted on me. How could it not?⁶⁰

A previous writer had described that "to listen to Lesego Rampolokeng's poetry is to experience the blunt brutality of the truth"⁵³. However, Deacy found a way through, writing at length about the collaborative process which led them to the final piece.

... initially could not see any way to make a collaborative piece with Lesego. His work I initially saw as complete with no room for anyone or anything else, but as I kept listening to his words and they became part of my day and this change, this space became a portal, and the possibilities were endless in the creation of something new in that space.

At this stage I got back in touch with Lesego and expressed my thoughts, as always he was so open minded, generous and supportive. He did not flinch when I asked could I make these little sound devices that when attached to hand held radios, the transmission of his words in the piece Riddim, Rime Reason would vibrate the hand of the holder and whatever they touched.

Power to the inspiration were his words.⁶⁰

Part III

Threads

In my ordering of Part II above, I followed the sequential experience of each work as directed by the exhibition map. In this part of the essay, I make meandering turns to connect the loose threads of socio-historical intertextual experience woven within the content and form across the exhibition.

In many ways, the artworks in this exhibition stand alone and are particular. The mediums differ greatly, sometimes even between works made by the same artist, as do their modes of engagement. However, threads and resonances emerge, as repetitions and re-negotiations of visual or aural motifs and themes, perhaps inevitable in an exhibition about unresolved questions and histories. Such resonances had a rhythmic quality, vibrating between the works and sometimes against them. The curator, Mestre, has anticipated this possibility, linking it to that of earlier art when conceiving the show.

The early stoneware from across Mesopotamia were decorated and inscribed in-the-round. On rotating the vessel, a pictorial design or textual patterning repeated itself eventually evolving into highly sophisticated visual narratives as reflected in African and Greek sequential imagery and text. Mirrored a thousand years later in the zoetrope and cinematic moving image, there is a conceptual leap from here to Plato's allegory of the cave imagining animated figures shadowed on walls, a few stepping-stones towards Freud's notion of the death drive, to impulsively repeat, to make and shape marks or words repetitively and sequentially.³

The collaborative ethos was to bring forth such connections and contrasts.

The idea was to match three artists from each country and for them to collaborate and that unfortunately had to take on other forms of collaborating or interchange. Key to the development of the works and the show itself was this idea of process. That the process we all went through at every level, would produce the work, produce the show. We have all been challenged and boundaries shifted - exciting, artists trying new things and new ways of working.¹⁴

However, the period scheduled for the collaboration was dramatically altered by Covid-19 pandemic restrictions. In both Ireland and South Africa severe restrictions were imposed to physical movement within the regions of each country and internationally. For an exhibition invested in engagement with site, the enforced interiority and barriers became a feature of the project. Already engaging with thematics of displacement, and forces that govern and restrict, the South African artists faced additional barriers to access the materiality of the site and also to the opportunities for engagement with networks, the press and the viewing public. Instead, their understandings of the site, surrounds, peoples and histories of Ireland were mediated by the local artists, the internet and literature. Affective commonalities emerged during the process, which crossed geographies and personal experiences. Mestre recounted that he drew on these to inform the installation.

In this process of making the works, and especially installing the works, it emerged we were all talking about similar things. Sense of anxiety, dread, uncertainty but there is humour, connection, beauty and tenderness and celebration.¹⁴

When experiencing the exhibition as a viewer, questions of the negotiation of place and of artistic practice emerged.

On place: Unmoored journeys through time and space

It is striking that in an exhibition about a site, the ground itself is un-constituted. Stained is the land under the viewer's feet, as Rampolokeng reminds that "blood-paths we travelled/ covered map your guilt's extent"¹. The horizon line is morphed into visualized data mappings of Covid-19 infection rates in Dixie's veils. In his discussion, the curator felt the exhibition showed "humankind existing in this constructed environment or artificial worlds".¹⁴

Figure 16: These details highlight the resonances between the 'passage' of trees and the materiality of the artworks of Dixie (left), Gallagher (middle) and Manifold (right) (Images by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

The *passage* between the traces of representational world and the canvas surface in Gallagher's painting enforces a sense of erosion. These landscape paintings are often without ground or sky, alluded to in colour washes absent of detail, contrasted by the hard linearity and use of black for trees and man-made objects. Even in those borderlines, there is bleeding between the constructed and the natural, where all are disassembled by human intervention, including invading exotic trees and hatchery detritus of industrial innovation⁴⁰. In other works, the lack of foreground appears similarly to the forest clearing of Manifold's video piece, as if a theatre emptied of the stage on which the performance plays out. This is not only about the disturbance of the unvigilant, but a place marked by histories of planned destruction and clearances.

*Malnutrition sown designed disease planted
 extinguishing new life fire drowning babies in slime
 meantime playing victim-innocence on the manhunt¹*

Figure 17: Visualisations of absence and other-worldliness across details of the artworks by Gallagher (left), Manifold (middle) and Dixie (right) (Image 1 and 3 by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Image 2 by Brent Mestre, Connemara, 2021)

In many works, the figure-ground relation is unmoored and unsettled. Pelsler's predator flies digitally, but the actual site is empty of presence. Ash falls in gravity-less movements, like blackened snow, *In the absence of air*. Astronauts, divers and child figures levitate in *Blueprint*. For Dixie, such disconnect to the natural order of gravity was to allude to "the idea

of things from outside of us, from outside the universe, impacting on us”⁴⁸. While Deacy’s tentative wish in *Eigentone* is for frequencies to enable connection across space, time and cultures; in most of the exhibition, references to the otherworldly - the cosmos, planets, fate, the divine, celestial, primordial - are shadow supplements to the harsh realities of material devastation in the artists’ midst.

levitate... see how far they fall¹

Against the speculative mirage and potential for escapism in futuristic outer space, are jolting juxtapositions, such as in this excerpt of *Bush Radio*, where the debased and bodily continues across into delusions of a better future.

Priest is Narcissist

Sticks his own balls Up his buttohole he’s that fantasist

Failing that turns pederast

That’s not in the past

History a trail of blood in semen to the present

Opposite meteorites

Shooting out dick-wads Futureward¹

In the wake of human destruction, we have no hero’s journey nor sympathetic human reference to guide us through the show, leaving us as viewers feeling exposed, isolated and, at points, culpable. Dixie’s silhouetted figures with their innards botanically exposed and Manifold’s truncated pairs of legs, are an emptying out of the human subject within the exhibition that is powerful.

Disembodied voices, detritus of human industry, severed medicalized limbs and diseased minds, spillage of fluids and waste. Rather than life-giving blood, Rampolokeng reveals “inhumanity courses through rotten veins” of some humans; while the pain of oppression is expressed as bodily pathology (“afraid to death living in palpitations endless”; “broken backs”; “legacy of bodies on conveyor belts/ Memories burning hot enough to make eyeballs melt”). The themes of scatology, vulgarity and death,⁷⁰ where in these works, it is humans who spread malaise, actual and ideological. In Dixie’s veils, we see the internal biology of the mapped insides of the human body cavity of three figures forming a line - not to receive vaccines but “to infect one another” where “the virus is being transmitted via a paintbrush”⁴⁸. The materiality of spray paint and ink splatter across the works, alluding to spit and fluids, marks that create chaos literally within the works and metaphorically in the world. Similarly, the recent vaccine imperialism of COVID is linked to much older histories of colonialists who settled as “disease transmitters by design/ parasites playing host/ nothing holy about the ghost” in *Bush Radio*. In another excerpt below, the contrast between the built tempo relating to the neglect of care for that of the living (‘weeds’; ‘blood’; ‘corpuscles’; ‘emaciated’) is contrasted with the quiet submission in the last line.

Babbling weeds like blood bubbles

the dance of corpuscles, fevered, frenzied, crazed, mad, emaciated and now

blessed be the economy emancipated.

Fortune to disembark the graveyard shuffle⁵⁵

In this graveyard shuffle, we see mutations of masked figures and hybridized appropriations of other artists’ figurines. Limbs of gods and mythological figures are revealed as “moral amputees/ arm stumped”⁵⁵. In *Blueprint to the Disorder of Things*, a disembodied hand emerges from the sky as a direct allusion to the iconography of the *dextera domini*, the desire to signify within artist representation the divine or his intermediaries, in early Christian medieval artworks. For Dixie this association was to communicate “this feeling of things coming from something that was out of our control, that was beyond our human experience almost”.⁴⁸

Against these forces, is the destruction of innocents, particularly children, usually vessels of hope for the future. Their vulnerability is intimated in the threat of action of the mythical figures in Manifold's and Gallagher's works, the pathologisation of the stunted *enfant* in Dixie's work; in the imagery of Rampolokeng ("drowning babies in slime"). This may be about the "death contract", witnessing bodies born out of acts of violence, perversion and violation; which are shaped by, or even because of, "abstract consciousness... that cannot apprehend or properly relate to others or reconcile its actions with the necessarily collective claims of sociality".⁵⁴

Such truncated economy of life, extends from the human child to fragile fauna and flora of the living world. The sitka trees from the surrounding man-made forest are visualised as figures, and similarly, in the experience of the viewer, they inhabit the site as distinct presences. In Gallagher's paintings, these brown and black painted specters loom; in Manifold's video their form is echoed in the truncated legs. In such ways, the artists allude to the damage of forest and landscape restoration initiatives that were shaped by colonial policy and practice which persist powerfully, but without ecological responsibility, today⁷¹.

Pelser explains that it was through interaction with Manifold that she gained an understanding of the local arts discourse of Galway and "decided to work with animals as intermediates of the environment"²⁵, with their associations of being tamed or wild. Manifold too evoked a bird figure, in her choice of association with the mythical The Morrigan, who was known to shapeshift into a crow before battle to foretell warriors of their fate.

Dixie has previously utilized domesticated dog character in her works as a foil to the human characters. The very same type appears in the *To Be King* video, and in both it holds the position of "the witness to the narrative that is unfolding"⁴⁸. Less ominous and active than the human figure, the dog sits, or lies down, with its head watching as actions unfold. Pelser's canine reference in her titling is indexical of uncertain conditions which engender questioning of that which is presented to you, through perceptions of what is known and visible (*canus familiarus*) and that unfamiliar and potentially dangerous (*canus lupus*).

*The French saying Entre Chien et Loup (between the dog and the wolf), this refers to the time in the evening when the light changes and so there is a shift of consciousness. When you cannot tell if it is a dog or a wolf.*²⁵

The quiet vigilance of Dixie's dog is notably different to the powerful movement of the birds which feature in the works of Pelser. For her, it was also an issue of the animal looking as predator with a god's eye of that within its sights.

*I wanted to work with the animals in the space either wild or farmed and I felt that the raptor spoke to surveillance and hunting.*²⁵

A spectral bird hunts absent fish. This is a world where animals inhabit our present to call us to the past. These figures were inhabitants of the space between dichotomies, enabling heterological understandings of the problematics of our times by engaging with instinct, emotion, the body, sexuality, the unconscious, violence and trauma. As the curator shared, it is an experience of the

*Slippage between the intangible and tangible the known and unknown; being stuck in that space of wilderness and taming or domesticating.*¹⁴

It is of interest that the South African artists, all of whom have had direct experience of wild animals, would chose not to picture animals of the continent of Africa, nor those more familiar to them personally or to local South African mythologies. This may be perhaps because the anticipated audience of the exhibition was European, to avoid the exoticization. Only one reference is made, to devastating effect in *Bush radio*, where animal imagery serves as a foil to the violence of humankind.

African stuffed animal cut tongue.

Ability to speak skin rug.

Lesson more precious than Persian bedside lamp.

The cranium eyeballs for torches sockets to the back wall.

Future projections the continents ahistorical darkness, hysterical.¹

On practice: Burdens of creativity and memory

Figure 18: Paint as representation and as wound, evoked in a detail of Gallagher's artworks (Image by Dina Zoe Belluigi, Connemara, 2021)

As much as these are artworks in dialogue with the space and the problematics of the time, they are also deliberations on art making and on being an artist. As such, I come full circle in this essay, back to the call made from the inner-outer sanctum to “listen at the lectern the great mortician/ at the morgue” of history. While artists may imagine themselves “as the self-appointed guardians of the public good”⁵⁴, the pandemic wreaked havoc with whatever fragile sense of value may have been demonstrated prior to it for artistic dissent⁷².

This is about a longer lineage, where the vessel is emblematic of artistic subjectivity. Within the Bible, the vessel is a metaphor for a person who places themselves as an instrument, a “lowly vessel”, to be utilized by a divine power or in service of a larger purpose. This inspiration tradition empties creativity of subjectivity, where the artist was seen as a ‘scriptor’ impersonally performing a public revelation of the divine. Humanist rejections of religion and indigenous

knowledge systems placed progress as possible through human effort and agency. To my reading, in this exhibition both such constructions are problematized. No longer the scribe at the service of communicating a supernatural message, whether from god or the ancestors, nor the humanist ideal of the potential for western creativity and innovation, artists in this exhibition are shown to be vessels broken, due to the abuses and excesses made in the name and interests of human power, and their precarious place in the neoliberal world order.

This is alluded to in Dixie's disease-spreading painter's hands and the appropriation of Velasquez's commissions of the powerful. It is explicit in the sense of foolishness and self-disgust of the artist being used, sanitising his work and being taintedness, within the political economy of the arts and its capitulation to capitalism, in Rampolokeng's work.

*Scoop up all the way the rhymes you memorize, separate them from slime
to recite on April Fools Day political tools come out to play.¹*

The artist figure is complicated in a number of works within this exhibition. There is little sense of the once shamanistic healer, except perhaps in the aspirations of Deacy. Rather there is capability, in the revelations of Gallagher's attraction to the aesthetics of the industrial and the austerity of sitka plantations; and in the overlaps of falsehood with truths, in Pelsner's sleight of hand. Entangled within the injunction to witness is the complicity of commemoration.

*Got truth to re-write/ unwrite
Genocide off the dark continent
Build a lie-monument¹*

Through such means, the exhibition reveals the complicated circumstances of artmaking and history writing in the shadow and light of apocalyptic devastation.

*One more page to one's fate
Nothing divine in destiny' manifest
Salvaged from Fires of Empire¹*

These words of Rampolokeng's bring to mind the pages of *Blueprint*, the references to mis-Fortune and the supernatural in Gallagher and Manifold, where the mundane realities are the embers, unnatural ash snow, surrounding us. These are artists of conscience wrestling with representing what they witness of human violence and the collapse of entire social, political and ecological systems at the hands of fellow humans.

While the work of freedom may require "a transformative relation with our past as a condition *sine qua non* of our control over our own future", the uncanny impression which remains after the exhibition, is of the artists' uncertainty, inversions, digressions, lamentations. Rampolokeng once spoke about the inevitable blurring between artistic form and artist knowing - the humility of knowing one is not an autonomous god-like seer but rather a product of the time which one is shaped by and critiques.

I think all of us are reservoirs of our experiences; from the moment of our conception to our death . . . Don't ask me to write about the "now" because I am still grappling with my past... I necessarily come out of this filth; my rhythm was created within the filth of this society. How is the reader to expect any kind of purity from my writing when it is born out of a decadent society?⁷³

In this exhibition, we can observe the artists' attempts to subvert hegemonic discourses with cultural expressions that are at times intimate, destabilising and catalytic. Rampolokeng and Dixie negotiate the literacy and aesthetic canons from which they appropriate; Manifold and Gallagher, the mythical and superstitious; Pelsner and Deacy, the technological. The force of confrontation in their revisionism and subterfuge differs, in no small part because their genealogies are heterological, and the extent of their vexation with, and grief, from injustice and inequality takes uneven forms.

From this failed cathedral of human agency, the tone that is struck is melancholic. Each piece a broken vessel to art itself, to the power and pitfalls of representation, wrought through the materiality of each medium, from the paint of Gallagher's canvases, through the static ruptures in Rampolokeng's rhythm, across the fading prints of Pelser's predators. Artists on the periphery witness the effects on the post-colony, their counter-shaping inverts, reformulates and decenters the authority of these systems of modernity's authority, as they enact the injunction to recall what may have been.

*The poet is he who, beneath the named,
constantly expected differences, rediscovers
the buried kinships between things, their
scattered resemblances. Beneath the
established signs, and in spite of them, he
hears another, deeper, discourse, which
recalls the time when words glittered in the
universal resemblance of things. (Michel Foucault *The Order of Things*)*

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References

- Albrecht, Glenn, Gina-Maree Sartore, Linda Connor, Nick Higginbotham, Sonia Freeman, Brian Kelly, Helen Stain, Anne Tonna, and Georgia Pollard. "Solastalgia: The Distress Caused by Environmental Change." *Australasian Psychiatry: Bulletin of Royal Australian and New Zealand College of Psychiatrists* 15 Suppl 1 (2007): S95-98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10398560701701288>.
- Allie, Mohammed. "South African Artists Struggle with Covid Theatre Closures." *BBC News*, April 9, 2021, sec. Africa. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-56651742>.
- Andrews, Kernan. "Sounds From The Countryside - a Sound Postcard." *Galway Advertiser*, May 21, 2021. <https://www.advertiser.ie/galway/article/114774/sounds-from-the-countryside-a-sound-postcard>.
- Architectural Association of Ireland. "AAI Awards 1990." Architectural Association of Ireland, 1990. <https://architecturalassociation.ie/awards/aai-awards-1990/>.
- Bailey, Blackjack. "Geocaching - The Official Global GPS Cache Hunt Site." *Geocaching*, December 12, 2007. <http://www.geocaching.com/>.
- Bartlett, Christy, Charly Iten, and Henry-James Holland. *Flickwerk: The Aesthetics of Mended Japanese Ceramics*. Museum für Lackkunst (Münster, Westfalen); Herbert F. Johnson Museum of Art, 2008. <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/7477034/flickwerk-the-aesthetics-of-mended-japanese-ceramics>.
- Belluigi, Dina Zoe. *Broken Vessels: The Im-Possibility of the Art of Remembrance and Re-Collection in the Work of Anselm Kiefer, Christian Boltanski, William Kentridge and Santu Mofokeng*. [S.l.: s.n.], 2001.

- Bocast, Chris. "Examining the Place of Music in Western Eco-Cosmology, with Implications for Electroacoustic Musical Practice." *Organised Sound* 17, no. 3 (December 2012): 240–47. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355771811000446>.
- Carney, Judith Ann, and Richard Nicholas Rosomoff. *In the Shadow of Slavery: Africa's Botanical Legacy in the Atlantic World*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2009.
- Carroll, Rory. "Ghost Ship Washes Ashore in Ireland after More than a Year at Sea." *The Guardian*, February 17, 2020, sec. World news. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/feb/17/ghost-ship-mv-alta-washes-ashore-ireland-year-sea-storm-dennis>.
- . "The Wrong Kind of Trees: Ireland's Afforestation Meets Resistance." *The Guardian*, July 7, 2019, sec. World news. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/jul/07/the-wrong-kind-of-trees-irelands-afforestation-meets-resistance>.
- Chaplin, Joyce E. "Can the Nonhuman Speak?: Breaking the Chain of Being in the Anthropocene." *Journal of the History of Ideas* 78, no. 4 (2017): 509/529. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jhi.2017.0029>.
- Clark, Rosalind. "Aspects of the Murrigan in Early Irish Literature." *Irish University Review* 17, no. 2 (1987): 223–36.
- Colwell, Mary. "A Forestry Boom Is Turning Ireland into an Ecological Dead Zone." *The Guardian*, October 10, 2018, sec. Opinion. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2018/oct/10/trees-ireland-biodiversity-sitka-birds-extinction>.
- Conley, Carolyn A. *Melancholy Accidents: The Meaning of Violence in Post-Famine Ireland*. Lanham, Md: Lexington Books, 1999.
- ConnollyCove. "Murals and Museums: Dark Tourism in Belfast." ConnollyCove. *History* (blog), n.d. <https://www.connollycove.com/murals-and-museums-dark-tourism-in-belfast/>.
- Cooper, Corinne Jane. "Composition Portfolio." Master of Music, Rhodes University, 2019. http://vital.seals.ac.za:8080/vital/access/manager/Repository/vital:41568?site_name=GlobalView.
- Dargie, David. "Umngqokolo: Xhosa Overtone Singing and the Song Nondel'ekhaya | African Music : Journal of the International Library of African Music." *African Music: Journal of the International Library of African Music* 7, no. 1 (1991): 33–47. <https://doi.org/10.21504/amj.v7i1.1928>.
- Deacy, Anne Marie. "Broken Vessel Exhibition," October 28, 2021.
- . "Music for Six Smart Phones." Anne Marie Deacy, 2020. <https://www.annemariedeacy.com/work/music-for-six-smart-phones>.
- . "RE: Vessels Essay," January 18, 2022.
- . "Talk during Walkabout at Culture Night." Inagh Valley, September 19, 2021.
- . "Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site." Unpublished, September 1, 2021.
- Dixie, Christine. "Personal Communication on Blueprint for the Disorder of Things." 64 powerpoint slides with audio recording by the artist, Makhanda, October 2021.
- . "Projects | The Disorder: Blueprint for the Disorder of Things | Christine Dixie." CD, 2020. <https://christinedixie.com/projects/the-disorder-blueprint-for-the-disorder-of-things>.
- Estes, Roberta. "Raleigh, a Wynganditoian." *Native Heritage Project* (blog), July 2, 2012. <https://nativeheritageproject.com/2012/07/02/raleigh-a-wynganditoian/>.
- Evans, Julia. "South Africa: Covid Funds for Artists - Public Protector Intervenes." *GroundUp*. May 21, 2021, sec. News. <https://allafrica.com/stories/202105210769.html>.
- Franca, J. L. Junior. "VERSES, SUBVERSES AND SUBVERSIONS IN CONTEMPORARY POSTCOLONIAL POETRY: The Arts of Resistance in the Works of Linton Kwesi Johnson and Lesego Rampolokeng." *Masters of Arts in Literary Studies, University of Cape Town*, 2009. <https://dlc.library.columbia.edu/catalog/ldpd:504770/bytestreams/content/content?filename=Jair+Fran%C3%A7a+Junior+.pdf>.
- Gallagher, Noelle. "Broken Vessels." Noelle Gallagher, 2021. <https://noellegallagher.com/broken-vessels>.
- . "Earlsfort Terrace." Describing Architecture, 2014. <http://www.describingarchitecture.com/portfolio/earlsfort-terrace-noelle-gallagher/>.
- . "Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site." Unpublished, September 1, 2021.

- Irish Famine Memorials. "Doolough, Co. Mayo (1994) Famine Memorial Inscriptions Commissioned by AFri." *Irish Famine Memorials* (blog), January 16, 2014. <https://irishfaminememorials.com/2014/01/16/doolough-co-mayo-1994/>.
- Irish Wildlife Trust. "Deer Culls." *Irish Wildlife Trust* (blog), August 7, 2015. <https://iwt.ie/deer-culls/>.
- Khazam, Rahma. "The Ambiguous Materiality of Sound - Springerin | Hefte Für Gegenwartskunst." *Springerin*, no. 1 (2012). <https://www.springerin.at/en/2012/1/greifbar-ungreifbar/>.
- Kwan, Pui Yang. "Exploring Japanese Art and Aesthetic as Inspiration for Emotionally Durable Design," 2–15. Hong Kong: www.designedasia.com, 2012. http://www.designedasia.com/2012/Full_Papers/Exploring%20Japanese%20Art%20and%20Aesthetic.pdf.
- Langbauer, William, Katherine B Payne, Russel A Charie, Lisa Rapaport, and Ferrel Osborn. "African Elephants Respond to Distant Playbacks of Low-Frequency Conspecific Calls." *Journal of Experimental Biology* 157, no. 1 (May 1, 1991): 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.157.1.35>.
- Lertzman, Renee. *Environmental Melancholia: Psychoanalytic Dimensions of Engagement*. London: Routledge, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315851853>.
- Maguire, F. "Tullybrack | The Schools' Collection." [duchas.ie](https://www.duchas.ie), 1893. <https://www.duchas.ie/en/cbes/5044784/5037752>.
- Manifold, Louise. "On Seaside Surrealism." In *All Mountains Begin on the Ground*, edited by Louise Manifold and Una Quigley. Unknown: Wild-Screen, 2015.
- . "Re: Vessels Essay," January 14, 2022.
- . "Some Info," October 24, 2021.
- . "Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site." Unpublished, September 1, 2021.
- McDevitt, Allan D., Ceiridwen J. Edwards, Peter O'Toole, Padruig O'Sullivan, Catherine O'Reilly, and Ruth F. Carden. "Genetic Structure of, and Hybridisation between, Red (Cervus Elaphus) and Sika (Cervus Nippon) Deer in Ireland." *Mammalian Biology* 74, no. 4 (July 1, 2009): 263–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mambio.2009.03.015>.
- Meistre, Brent. "Broken Vessel, Exhibition Guide and Map." Interface; Analogue Eye, 2001.
- . "Broken Vessels Information Pack for Press." Unpublished, 2021.
- . "Walkabout Notes." Inagh, Ireland, September 17, 2021.
- Miller, Moshe. "Shattered Vessels - Introduction to the Ari's Concept of Shevirat HaKeilim." Kabbalah Online, 2010. https://www.chabad.org/kabbalah/article_cdo/aid/380568/jewish/Shattered-Vessels.htm.
- Mkhize, Khwezi. "Neither History nor Freedom Will Absolve Us: On the Ethical Dimensions of the Poetry of Lesego Rampolokeng." *Safundi* 12, no. 2 (April 1, 2011): 179–202. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17533171.2011.557192>.
- Mofokeng, Phehello. "'It Takes a Ripple to Make a Storm': A Reflection on Lesego Rampolokeng's Poetry - BKO Magazine." *BKO Africa Is a State of Mind* (blog), December 18, 2020. <https://bkomagazine.co.za/editor-at-large-phehello-j-mofokeng-reflects-on-lesego-rampolokengs-oeuvre-from-a-personal-point-of-view/>.
- Murray, Joe. "Desmond Tutu Was a Giant for Justice and His Legacy Lives On." *Irish Examiner*, December 27, 2021. <https://www.irishexaminer.com/opinion/commentanalysis/arid-40773504.html>.
- O'Connell, Michael. "Post-Glacial Vegetation and Landscape Change in Upland Ireland with Particular Reference to Mám Éan, Connemara." *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 290 (July 1, 2021): 104377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.revpalbo.2021.104377>.
- Pelser, Monique. "Broken Vessels Exhibition," October 12, 2021.
- . "RE: Vessels Essay," January 24, 2022.
- . "Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site." Unpublished, 2021.
- Rainsford, Sue. *Air Looms. Louise Manifold. Curator Sarah Searson. 14 November 2020- 6 March 2021*. Carrick-on-Shannon: www.thedock.ie, 2020.
- Rampolokeng, Lesego. *Excerpts of Transcriptions of the Audio of Bush Radio*. 2021.
- . "Riddim, Rime, Reason." *The Artist*, December 6, 2021.
- Robins, Alannah. *Hatchery*. Accessed November 5, 2021. <https://interfaceinagh.com/product/hatchery/>.
- . *Introduction to the Broken Vessels Walkabout*. Inagh Valley, 2021.
- Robinson, Tom. "Connemara after the Famine." *History Ireland*, 1996. <https://www.historyireland.com/18th-19th-century-history/connemara-after-the-famine/>.
- Said, Edward W. *Culture and Imperialism*. London: Chatto & Windus, 1993.

- Schwartz, Stephanie. "David Levi Strauss: Photography and Belief • Jörg Colberg: Photography's Neoliberal Realism." *Art Monthly*, no. 443 (2021): 2.
- Siggins, Lorna. "Dead Fish in Connemara Lake Are Linked to Salmon Hatchery." *The Irish Times*, October 14, 2000. <https://www.irishtimes.com/news/dead-fish-in-connemara-lake-are-linked-to-salmon-hatchery-1.1109118>.
- Soltis, Joseph, Kirsten Leong, and Anne Savage. "African Elephant Vocal Communication II: Rumble Variation Reflects the Individual Identity and Emotional State of Callers." *Animal Behaviour* 70, no. 3 (September 1, 2005): 589–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2004.11.016>.
- Sousa Santos, Boaventura de. "Beyond Abyssal Thinking - Boaventura de Sousa Santos From Global Lines to Ecologies of Knowledges." *Review XXX*, no. 1 (2007): 1–66.
- Strauss, David Levi. *Photography and Belief*. David Zwirner Books, 2020.
- Taylor, Timothy D. "The Gendered Construction of the Musical Self: The Music of Pauline Oliveros." *The Musical Quarterly* 77, no. 3 (1993): 385–96.
- The Irish Memorial. "Famine Pot." *The Irish Memorial* (blog), n.d. <https://www.irishmemorial.org/famine-pot/>.
- Venter, Pieter J., and Johan J. Hanekom. "Automatic Detection of African Elephant (*Loxodonta Africana*) Infrasonic Vocalisations from Recordings." *Biosystems Engineering* 106, no. 3 (July 1, 2010): 286–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2010.04.001>.
- Vetter, Susanne. "With Power Comes Responsibility – A Rangelands Perspective on Forest Landscape Restoration." *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 4 (2020): 225. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.549483>.
- Watson, Chris. *SHORTLY BEFORE SUNRISE, THE SPIRITS OF THE NIGHT DANCE THEIR LAST DANCE*. Glasbeck, Germany, 2021. <https://chriswatson.net/2021/07/06/ruhrtriennale-maschinenhalle-zweckel-gladbeck-germany-14th-august-2021/>.
- Wikipedia. "Souperism." In *Wikipedia*, July 17, 2021. <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Souperism&oldid=1034022471>.
- Wood, Tahir. "'You Are Subjects!' Higher Education and the General Intellect." *Journal of Education and Work* 18, no. 3 (September 1, 2005): 341–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080500200609>.

List of artworks

(In alphabetical order)

- Anne Marie Deacy. 2021 Eigentone: 126.22Hz - 221.23Hz. Four channel audio, wood, galvanised steel.
- Anne Marie Deacy and Lesego Rampolekeng. 2021. Riddim Rhyme Reason on Culture Night. Interactive sound installation with audience participation, transmitter and tuning forks.
- Christine Dixie. 2021. Blueprint for the Disorder of Things. 8 inkjet prints, spraypaint, mosquito net.
- Christine Dixie. 2021. Blueprint for a Breathless World. Single channel HD video via QR code (7min 22s). <https://christinedixie.com/channel>
- Noelle Gallagher. 2021. Fortuna's Wheel. Oil paint on canvas, board, digital print, single channel HD video projection (2min 15sec).
- Monique Pelser. 2021. Shortly before sunrise, the spirits of the night dance their last dance. 2000 A4 inkjet prints, pasted A4 laserjet prints, Google VR interface sequences via Instagram, (QR codes).
- Louise Manifold. 2021. In the absence of air. Single channel HD video projection (5min 54sec).
- Louise Manifold. 2021. Visitors. Water fountain pump, memorial wreath.
- Lesego Rampolokeng. 2021. Bush Radio 94.4FM. Portable FM radios, FM transmitter, audio recording (23min 56s).

Endnotes

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- ¹ Rampolokeng, *Excerpts of Transcriptions of the Audio of Bush Radio*.
- ² Carroll, "Ghost Ship Washes Ashore in Ireland after More than a Year at Sea."
- ³ Mestre, "Broken Vessels Information Pack for Press".
- ⁴ Carney and Rosomoff, *In the Shadow of Slavery*.
- ⁵ The Irish Memorial, "Famine Pot."
- ⁶ Conley, *Melancholy Accidents*.
- ⁷ Wikipedia, "Souperism."
- ⁸ The inscriptions on the monument erected as a part of this interaction are telling: SIDE 1 reads "Unveiled by / Karen Gearon, / Dunnes Stores Strikers, / 7th May 1994. / Erected by AFri"; SIDE 2, "In 1991 we walked AFri's / Great Famine walk at Doolough / And soon afterwards we / Walked the road to freedom / in South Africa / Archbishop Desmond Tutu"; SIDE 3, "To Commemorate / The Hungry Poor / who walked here in 1849 / and walk the Third World today / Freedom for South Africa 1994 / 'How can men feel themselves / Honoured by the humiliation / of their fellow beings' / Mahatma Gandhi in South Africa" Irish Famine Memorials, "Doolough, Co. Mayo (1994) Famine Memorial Inscriptions Commissioned by AFri"; Murray, "Desmond Tutu Was a Giant for Justice and His Legacy Lives On."
- ⁹ ConnollyCove, "Murals and Museums."
- ¹⁰ Robinson, "Connemara after the Famine."
- ¹¹ Siggins, "Dead Fish in Connemara Lake Are Linked to Salmon Hatchery."
- ¹² Miller, "Shattered Vessels - Introduction to the Ari's Concept of Shevirat HaKeilim."
- ¹³ Bartlett, Iten, and Holland, *Flickwerk*; Kwan, "Exploring Japanese Art and Aesthetic as Inspiration for Emotionally Durable Design."
- ¹⁴ Mestre, "Walkabout Notes."
- ¹⁵ This aligns with the ethos of the curators' larger project, *Analogue Eye: Video Art Africa*, which utilizes the *analogue* of production and display of video art works in ways which work against the seamlessness of contemporary *digital* and cinematic production and representations in the cultural mass media. See <https://www.mestre.org/>
- ¹⁶ Belluigi, *Broken Vessels*.
- ¹⁷ Lertzman, *Environmental Melancholia*.
- ¹⁸ For more on this initiative see <https://interfaceinagh.com/>
- ¹⁹ Robins, *Hatchery*.
- ²⁰ O'Connell, "Post-Glacial Vegetation and Landscape Change in Upland Ireland with Particular Reference to Mám Éan, Connemara."
- ²¹ Architectural Association of Ireland, "AAI Awards 1990."
- ²² Robins, *Introduction to the Broken Vessels Walkabout*.
- ²³ Mestre, "Broken Vessel, Exhibition Guide and Map."
- ²⁴ Strauss, *Photography and Belief*; Schwartz, "David Levi Strauss: Photography and Belief • Jörg Colberg: Photography's Neoliberal Realism."
- ²⁵ Pelser, "Broken Vessels Exhibition," October 12, 2021.
- ²⁶ Pelser, "RE: Vessels Essay," January 24, 2022.
- ²⁷ Pelser, "Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site."
- ²⁸ Pelser (2021) attributed this interest in Watson's work to her interaction with Deacy, one of the Irish artists, with whom she engaged during this project.
- ²⁹ Watson, *SHORTLY BEFORE SUNRISE, THE SPIRITS OF THE NIGHT DANCE THEIR LAST DANCE*.
- ³⁰ Manifold, "Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site."
- ³¹ Clark, "Aspects of the Morrigan in Early Irish Literature," 223.
- ³² Colwell, "A Forestry Boom Is Turning Ireland into an Ecological Dead Zone."
- ³³ Manifold, "Re: Vessels Essay," January 14, 2022.
- ³⁴ Rainsford, *Air Looms. Louise Manifold. Curator Sarah Se arson. 14 November 2020- 6 March 2021*.
- ³⁵ Manifold, "Some Info," October 24, 2021.
- ³⁶ Bailey, "Geocaching - The Official Global GPS Cache Hunt Site."
- ³⁷ Maguire, "Tullybrack | The Schools' Collection."
- ³⁸ Gallagher, "Broken Vessels."
- ³⁹ Carroll, "The Wrong Kind of Trees."
- ⁴⁰ Gallagher, "Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site."
- ⁴¹ Chaplin, "Can the Nonhuman Speak?: Breaking the Chain of Being in the Anthropocene."

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- ⁴² McDevitt et al., “Genetic Structure of, and Hybridisation between, Red (Cervus Elaphus) and Sika (Cervus Nippon) Deer in Ireland.”
- ⁴³ Irish Wildlife Trust, “Deer Culls.”
- ⁴⁴ Ireland's Animals by Niall Mac Coitir
- ⁴⁵ Gallagher, “Earlsfort Terrace.”
- ⁴⁶ Albrecht et al., “Solastalgia.”
- ⁴⁷ Manifold, “On Seaside Surrealism.”
- ⁴⁸ Dixie, “Personal Communication on Blueprint for the Disorder of Things”
- ⁴⁹ Dixie, “Projects | The Disorder : Blueprint for the Disorder of Things | Christine Dixie.”
- ⁵⁰ Dixie explained in personal communication (11/1/2022) that she had purchased the mask from a trader during the National Arts Festival, in her home town of Makanda around 2018. “He couldn't give me much info on it, but it has similar features to an Igbo White Spirit Maiden Mask that I saw in the Wits Art Collection and that Anita Nettleton identified for me. I think my mask, though it looks quite authentic, is probably more for tourists, this is because there are not holes to see out of where the eyes are, so it probably wouldn't have been used in a ritual, unlike the 'real' thing. The White Spirit Maidens assisted in travelling between our world and the spirit world - not unlike the function of the plague doctor at the end of a life I guess”.
- ⁵¹ Dargie, “Umngqokolo.”
- ⁵² Cooper, “Composition Portfolio.”
- ⁵³ Mofokeng, “It Takes a Ripple to Make a Storm.”
- ⁵⁴ Mkhize, “Neither History nor Freedom Will Absolve Us”.
- ⁵⁵ Rampolokeng, “Riddim, Rime, Reason.”
- ⁵⁶ Franca, “VERSES, SUBVERSES AND SUBVERSIONS IN CONTEMPORARY POSTCOLONIAL POETRY: The Arts of Resistance in the Works of Linton Kwesi Johnson and Lesego Rampolokeng,” 6.
- ⁵⁷ Estes, “Raleigh, a Wynganditoian.”
- ⁵⁸ Said, *Culture and Imperialism*, 260.
- ⁵⁹ de Sousa Santos, “Beyond Abyssal Thinking - Boaventura de Sousa Santos From Global Lines to Ecologies of Knowledges.”
- ⁶⁰ Deacy, “Broken Vessel Exhibition,” October 28, 2021.
- ⁶¹ Khazam, “The Ambiguous Materiality of Sound - Springerin | Hefte Für Gegenwartskunst.”
- ⁶² Deacy, “RE: Vessels Essay,” January 18, 2022.
- ⁶³ Taylor, “The Gendered Construction of the Musical Self.”
- ⁶⁴ Deacy, “Text on the Artworks Available at the Exhibition Site.”
- ⁶⁵ Bocast, “Examining the Place of Music in Western Eco-Cosmology, with Implications for Electroacoustic Musical Practice.”
- ⁶⁶ Deacy, “Talk during Walkabout at Culture Night.”
- ⁶⁷ Andrews, “Sounds From The Countryside - a Sound Postcard.”
- ⁶⁸ Deacy, “Music for Six Smart Phones.”
- ⁶⁹ I am not expert in this area, and so defer here a number of texts on the subject for the interested reader. Soltis, Leong, and Savage, “African Elephant Vocal Communication II”; Langbauer et al., “African Elephants Respond to Distant Playbacks of Low-Frequency Conspecific Calls”; Wood, “‘You Are Subjects!’ Higher Education and the General Intellect”; Venter and Hanekom, “Automatic Detection of African Elephant (*Loxodonta Africana*) Infrasonic Vocalisations from Recordings.”
- ⁷⁰ See Esty's “Excremental Postcolonialism,” and Mbembe's “The Banality of Power and the Aesthetics of Vulgarity in the Postcolony” which are discussed by Mkhize, “Neither History nor Freedom Will Absolve Us,” 186 ft 33.
- ⁷¹ Vetter, “With Power Comes Responsibility – A Rangelands Perspective on Forest Landscape Restoration.”
- ⁷² Allie, “South African Artists Struggle with Covid Theatre Closures”; Evans, “South Africa.”
- ⁷³ Rampolokeng interviewed by Ijeoma Akunyili in Mkhize, “Neither History nor Freedom Will Absolve Us,” 197.